

Integration Possibilities of Dyeing and Hydrophobic Finishing Processes for Cotton Fiber Textile Fabrics

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Abstrakt

In this work, the possibilities of combining the processes of dyeing and hydrophobic properties of cotton textile fabrics were investigated. The study examined the influence of various technological sequences of dyeing and final finishing processes, as well as methods for performing them in a single stage, on the physical, mechanical, color, and operational properties of the fabric. The results obtained showed that single-stage dyeing and finishing technology not only improves fabric strength, color intensity, and color fastness but also effectively ensures water-repelling properties.

Key words: cotton fabric, dyeing, finishing, hydrophobic.

Аннотация: В данной работе исследованы возможности сочетания процессов окрашивания и придания гидрофобных свойств хлопчатобумажным текстильным тканям. В исследованиях изучено влияние различных технологических последовательностей процессов окрашивания и финишной отделки, а также способов их осуществления в один этап на физико-механические, колористические и эксплуатационные свойства ткани. Полученные результаты показали, что одноступенчатая технология окрашивания-аппретирования эффективно обеспечивает не только улучшение прочности ткани, интенсивности и стойкости цвета, но и водоотталкивающие свойства.

Ключевые слова: ткань хлопчатобумажная, крашение, заключительная отделка, гидрофобность.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu ishda paxta tolali to‘qimachilik matolarini bo‘yash va gidrofob xossa berish jarayonlarini birlashtirish imkoniyatlari tadqiq qilingan. Tadqiqotlarda bo‘yash va yakuniy pardozlash jarayonlarini turli texnologik ketma-ketliklarda olib borish hamda ularni bir bosqichda amalga oshirish usullarining matoning fizik-mexanik, koloristik va ekspluatatsion xossalariga ta’siri o‘rganildi. Olingan natijalar bir bosqichli bo‘yash-appretlash texnologiyasining mato mustahkamligi, rang intensivligi va rang mustahkamligini yaxshilash bilan bir qatorda suv itaruvchanlik xossalarini ham samarali ta’minlashini ko‘rsatdi.

Kalit so‘zlar: paxta tolali mato, bo‘yash, yakuniy pardoz, gidrofob.

Currently, the integration of dyeing and functional finishing processes for cotton fiber textile fabrics represents one of the most relevant directions in the development of resource-efficient and environmentally sustainable technologies. In conventional technologies, the separate execution of these processes leads to increased consumption of water, energy, and chemical agents [1]. Recent scientific studies have demonstrated that conducting dyeing and finishing operations in a single stage can significantly enhance production efficiency [2]. Such integrated technologies contribute to reducing the number of processing steps while maintaining fabric quality.

In addition, nanoparticles, sol–gel systems, and surface chemical modification methods are widely employed to impart hydrophobic properties to cotton fabrics. These approaches reduce the surface energy of the fabric and form a stable water-repellent layer on the material surface [3]. As a result, the integration of dyeing and hydrophobic finishing processes for cotton fabrics is considered one of the highly efficient, environmentally friendly, and advanced textile technologies with significant scientific and practical importance [4].

The possibility of combining dyeing and final finishing processes was investigated in this study. Different technological sequences were examined, including: treatment of the fabric with a finishing solution followed by dyeing with a reactive dye, application of the finishing process after dyeing, and simultaneous implementation of both processes in a single bath. The one-step dyeing and finishing method was carried out in two different media. In the first bath, the alkaline agent and SAM, which are components of the dyeing solution, were excluded from the formulation. In the second bath, acetic acid and Kollasol CDO, which are components of the finishing formulation, were omitted. The experimental results obtained are presented in Table 1.

Table 1.

Influence of the Sequence of Dyeing and Finishing Processes on the Performance Properties of Woven Fabrics

Fabric Performance Properties	Finishing -Dyeing	Dyeing - Finishing	Simultaneous Dyeing and Finishing (without Alkali)	Simultaneous Dyeing and Finishing (in Alkaline Medium)
Breaking Strength, N:	609,2	599,4	632,7	643,5
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Weft direction • Warp direction 	328,6	355,1	387,5	395,3
Elongation at Break, %:	20,5	20,2	19,4	17,3
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Weft direction • Warp direction 	17,6	18,2	18,7	18,9
Air Permeability, $\text{dm}^3/\text{m}^2 \cdot \text{s}$	160,0	172,0	188,0	155,0
Hydrostatic Water Resistance, mm H ₂ O	320,0	340,0	300,0	370,0

Color Strength, K/S.	9,5	12	10	14
Color Fastness to Soaping (rating)	4/4/3	5/5/5	4/3/3	5/5/5
Dyeing Levelness, %	1,2	0,9	0,8	0,9

The obtained results indicate that the samples treated by the sequence of impregnation in a reactive dye solution, squeezing and application of finishing agents, drying, and thermal treatment, as well as those treated by simultaneous application of finishing and reactive dye solutions in an alkaline medium followed by drying and thermal treatment, exhibited higher coloristic properties compared to other methods. The covalent bonds formed between the fiber and dye molecules in an alkaline medium ensured improved color fastness. In addition, due to the formation of a thin film layer on the fabric surface, the samples treated in a single-bath acidic system demonstrated the highest hydrophobic properties. Although sequential dyeing and finishing processes provided satisfactory color fastness and levelness, partial desorption of the dye into the finishing solution led to a decrease in color strength. Moreover, the possibility of reusing the finishing solution becomes more complicated in this case. The improvement of physical and mechanical properties in both single-bath dyeing–finishing processes, compared to the separate application of these processes, can be explained by the formation of an elastic thin film on the fabric surface during thermal treatment due to the fixing component present in the finishing formulation. In contrast, in fabrics first dyed and then finished, the roughness of the formed surface film reduced fabric elasticity, resulting in lower breaking strength values. Based on the conducted studies and analyses, the following composition and procedure for imparting hydrophobic properties to cotton fabrics are proposed:

1. Impregnation, g/L → Squeezing → Drying → Thermal treatment

CH ₃ COOH (80%-) – 1,0 OP-10 – 0,3 Tubiguard SCS - T – 40 PVA – 15	100%	T ⁰ C - 90	T ⁰ C - 150 T – 1-1,5 daq.
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2. Impregnation, g/L

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Drying

→

**Thermal
treatment**

Reactive dye – 5
NaCl – 30
NaOH – 2
OP-10 – 0,3
Tubiguard SCS - T – 40
PVA – 15

T⁰C - 90

T⁰C - 150
T – 1-1,5 daq.

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